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Initial definition of the scientific challenges and initial evaluation plan - Controlling plasma-material interfaces with BIT

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable we describe BIT1 code profiling results, discuss them and perform the corresponding gap analysis.

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1 Introduction

The leading design of the fusion reactor is called a tokamak due to the toroidal shape of the reactor chamber and the magnetic confinement of the plasma. Tokamak is also the selected design of the future largest experimental fusion reactors ITER [www.iter.org] and DEMO, whose role is to prove the feasibility of fusion energy. In a tokamak, confinement is enabled by employing an external toroidal magnetic field and a poloidal field, which is a result of toroidal current induced in plasma. The confinement is not and cannot be perfect and there is a constant outflux of particles and energy from the core plasma, which is at least partially beneficial. But this does lead to one of the fundamental issues of fusion reactors. Namely, the plasma must be confined at almost vacuum-like pressure, which imposes the need for a solid chamber around it. The problem stems from the fact, that any solid (tungsten is currently the main option) has a much lower melting temperature than the core plasma. In modern tokamaks this issue is approached by setting up an intermediate layer of plasma between the solid surface and the core plasma. This plasma is called the scrape-off-layer (SOL).

The SOL plasma is not magnetically closed, as the open field lines drive it to the bottom part of the reactor, named the divertor. The divertor is designed in a way that it can sustain high plasma heat fluxes, however future large tokamaks will push the divertor materials to their limits.

There are several approaches to modelling of tokamak SOL plasmas, depending on the precision of description. The traditional one is the fluid approach, when plasma transport is described by a fluid model. Recent investigations demonstrate that for the next generation fusion devices kinetic effects in the SOL play an important role and thus, the fluid models have to be complemented by the kinetic study [1]. In the present project we consider a 1D3V electrostatic Particle-in Cell Monte Carlo (PIC MC) code BIT1 suitable for parallel transport of plasma, neutral and impurity particles in the SOL. BIT1 has a good scaling for up to 10-20 thousands of cores enabling simulations of future tokamaks like ITER. The goal of the project to significantly increase the scaling of code so that ITER SOL simulations can be performed within one week and kinetic modelling of the even larger future tokamak, DEMO, becomes a realistic task.

2 Definition of the Scientific Challenge

2.1 Relevance and Physical Background

Fully kinetic study of the plasma, impurity and neutral particle transport in the SOL is an extremely challenging task. BIT1 considers only 1D transport enabling investigation of a number of essential kinetic effects, such as

- i the contribution of non-Maxwellian particles to the divertor heat fluxes;
- ii effects of the de-magnetization of the plasma-wall interaction layer;
- iii time dependent heat fluxes to the divertors during the so-called Edge Localized Modes (ELM), and

iv W (tungsten) net sputtering rates from the divertor plates.

These effects will significantly influence plasma performance and lifetime of divertor plates in future tokamaks such as COMPASS-U, DTT, ITER and DEMO. At present, BIT1 is a unique kinetic code contributing to all these studies.

2.2 Detailed Definition of the Simulation Setup

The final target of the project is to perform simulations of the ITER SOL for ELM-ing SOL at ITER and predict power and particle loads to the divertor plates and W net erosion rates. Simulations will consist of three parts: pre-, intra- and after-ELM phases in the SOL. The updated code should be able to perform simulations within 3 weeks (one week per phase). Such reduction of the simulation time will enable multiple simulation runs in a reasonable time, so that we could perform scanning over different input parameters. We consider basic ELMy H-Mode discharges at ITER, with the duration of ELM reconnection 0.5 ms. We consider the same simulation time for the pre- and after-ELM phases.

One of the main control parameters of the PIC simulation of the SOL is the shorting factor (see [2]), which represents the ratio of real to the simulated size of the SOL. The simulation speed typically scales as square of shorting factor. Although, it has been demonstrated that simulations with a shorting factor below 30 well describe the realistic SOL, it is still beneficial to use its as small as possible values. Up to present, for ITER simulations we were using shorting factor 20 [3]. Our aim is to use smaller shorting number (10) which will require $5 \cdot 10^6$ grid cells along the poloidal direction. Required average number of simulation particles per cell is 300, thus total number of simulation particles is expected to be $N_{par} = 1.5 \cdot 10^9$.

The time step required for the ITER simulation (defined by PIC requirements) is $dt = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-13}$ s; therefore, for simulation of the intra-ELM phase $N_{dt} = 3.4 \cdot 10^8$ time steps are required (for the shorting number 10). Therefore, the target simulation size (per SOL phase) is $H = N_{par} \cdot N_{dt} = 5 \cdot 10^{17}$ particle time steps.

3 Gap analysis

PIC MC modelling of the ITER SOL represents an extremely complex physics task; therefore, we consider a more simplified physics model, plasma sheath, requiring the similar numerical effort as SOL modelling. The profiling results presented here correspond to the simulations performed on KTH HPE Cray EX *Dardel* supercomputer [4]; SOL simulations discussed below were performed on the CINECA's *Marconi* supercomputer.

3.1 Downscaling the Target Case

The existing BIT1 simulations of the ITER SOL represent the pre-ELM phase with a shorting factor 20 [3]. Simulations follow $5.2 \cdot 10^8$ simulation particles for 10 time steps and require $2.4 \cdot 10^6$ spatial grid cells, thus simulation size is $H_0 = N_{par} \cdot N_{dt} = 2.6 \cdot 10^{16}$ particle time steps. Simulations were performed on 4608 cores for overall $t_0 = 7 \cdot 10^6$ core hours.

L1 Load Misses	Baseline Size	10% Reduced size	20% Reduced size	Cache test
L1 Load Misses	3.43	2.51	2.17	5.53
LLC Load Misses	99.07	52.25	47.51	18.95

Table 1: Cache misses (in percentage) for the baseline and 10% and 20% reduces size simulations. "Cache test" corresponds to a very simple test function.[4]

3.2 Initial Performance Analysis

We considered two simulation cases: a small size run, "Ionization", (just to have a reference) and the plasma sheath model mentioned above. The outcomes of the BIT1 profiling are listed below.

1. The performance of BIT1 depends on the problem size and effective LLC (Last Level Cache) usage; the BIT1 is a highly memory-bound code (see Table 1).
2. There is some workload imbalance: MPI rank 0 is the slowest and other neighbor MPI processes waiting for it (see Figure1); explanation: the Rank 0 gathers and sends some general data to other ranks.
3. At large number of MPI processes, BIT1 is subject to a self-synchronization process, degrading the overall parallel performance; explanation: The Field solver, as well as plasma profile calculator require synchronization.

Figure 1: Rank communication for the simple run. [4]

4. The main CPU time consumers are the following functions: `arrj()`, `moveb()` and `bincc_dspf()` (see Figure 2).
 - `arrj()` sorts particles into proper cells and puts "outsiders" into the buffer cells. The latter (in other function calls) will be sent to the neighboring ranks or removed from the simulation. Also here no rank communication is required. We think this function can be further optimized (see next section).
 - `moveb()` is one of the particle pushers using the Leap-Frog scheme. It is already highly optimized: adjusts solver to the given magnetic field geometry and uses minimum possible floating operations; it does not require rank communication

- `bincc_dspf()` is a Binary collision operator. It does not require rank communication and is already optimized.

Figure 2: Percentage breakdown of the BIT1 functions for the simple and the productive runs.[4]

5. BIT1 exhibits hyper-scaling for large size simulations, see Figure 3.

3.3 Performance Projection to the Target Case for Exascale

From the obtained profiling results and simplified ITER modelling we can now estimate the Figure of Merit (FOM) for the exascale BIT1:

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{H \cdot t_0}{H_0 \cdot \text{”One – week – in – hours”}} \approx 9.0 \cdot 10^4 \text{cores},$$

where, $H = 5 \cdot 10^{17}$ and $H_0 = 2.6 \cdot 10^{16}$ particle time steps are the sizes of the exascale and the original simulation, respectively, and $t_0 = 7 \cdot 10^6$ core hours is the clock time for the original simulation.

This target can be reached by combination of the increasing scaling of BIT1 and its simulation speed (for the fixed number of used cores); e.g. it will be sufficient to achieve good scaling of BIT for $9.0 \cdot 10^4$ cores. Assuming good scaling of the present version of BIT1 for 10^4 cores, we end up with the speed up requirement by the factor 9. Here we assumed that the speed up is done exclusively by increasing the number of MPI processes.

4 Roadmap for Development

4.1 Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code

As it was mentioned in the previous section, we can identify the following bottlenecks:

1. The function `arrj()` used for sorting of particles; This function runs over all simulation particles and uses up to 4 “if” statements, as well removes particles crossing

Figure 3: BIT1 strong scaling. “Ionization” denotes a simplified small size simulation with a scaling saturated at 2500 cores and even its degradation with increasing core number. This behaviour is caused by the reduction of the simulation area per core, leading to the increase of the relative number of particles passed to the neighbouring cores and to the overall degradation of performance. The large productive run, “Sheath”, is characterised by a large number of simulation particles per core and shows hyper-scaling. The later seem to be caused by the memory bound at lower number of cores. “Ideal” curves correspond to the linear scaling of the simulation speed with the core number.[4]

grid cell boundaries (functions `rempart2()` and `rempart3()`). One has to note that the function `moveb()` also runs over all simulation particles. It does not use “if” statements and particle removal, but performs more than 10 float operations per particle (i.e. more than in `arrj()`); still it is almost 3 times faster than the `arrj()` function. Therefore, we conclude that “if” statements and particle removal probably are responsible for slowing down of the `arrj()` function.

2. Significant memory bound.
3. Nonuniform work balance. The reason of this is bottleneck is a non-uniform distribution of simulation particles between different ranks. At present, BIT1 uses uniform space decomposition and fixed weights of simulation particles; therefore, the number of simulation particles per rank is proportional to the local plasma density. As a result, in plasma edge (with strongly nonuniform density profiles) different ranks handle different number of simulation particles.

4.2 Next Steps Planned

First, we want to study upper limit of the BIT1 scaling: as one can see from the Figure 3, the BIT1 scaling for large scale problems does not saturate and even increases at maximum tested core number, 18 000.

As next steps:

1. We develop a more optimized version of the `arrj()` function and plan to perform a new set of BIT1 profiling. Also, we want to investigate the CPU time used by the functions `rempart2()` and `rempart3()` responsible for simulation particle removal. If the latter will be too large, we might develop alternative way for particle removal.
2. At present, we do not have a strategy for removing this bottleneck. One possible solution might be dynamical memory allocation discussed below.
3. One of the possibilities to mitigate this problem is to introduce nonuniform space decomposition in BIT1, so that each rank gets approximately the same number of simulation particles. This will require very significant updates of the BIT1 code and first we will wait for the outcomes of the task 1. Then if proceeded, the nonuniform space decomposition should be performed in two steps: 1. fixed in time nonuniform space decomposition, and if it will be successful, 2. the dynamical space decomposition. The former will be tested for stationary problems and the latter for the time dependent ones.

5 Software Engineering Status and Plan

5.1 Copyright and license

BIT1 uses the defined non-GPL Free Customised licence (request to IPP CAS), <https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1/-/wikis/home>. Copyright entirely lies on the IPP CAS.

5.2 Development process and coding standards

BIT1 is hosted on GitHub (<https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1>) with a copy at UL. Only the main developer, D. Tskhakaya, has push rights to the repository.

There is a code manual describing main steps for code development and maintenance (<https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1/-/wikis/home>).

5.3 Bug tracking

The GitHub issue tracker is not used.

5.4 Documentation and user support

Code documentation including the user manual is kept on the GitLab <https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1/-/wikis/home>; it is systematically updated by the main developer. We plan to use Autogenerated `doxygen` documentation.

5.5 Requirements handling

BIT1 uses only the standard libraries. This strategy has been introduced to achieve maximum flexibility and portability. Code is relatively easy to implement and maintain on a variety of different-sized platforms.

5.6 Continuous Integration and Testing

A set of test input files are generated and used for "manual" verification of new releases of the code. A continuous integration process has recently been set up on the basis of GitHub actions at the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project and is slowly being integrated into the day-to-day development activities.

5.7 Release process

Releases are made by the main developer.

5.8 Deployment

BIT1 source code can be directly downloaded from its GitLab by the authorised users, or can be provided by the main developer.

5.9 Deprecation

There is currently no structured process for removal of old features. At irregular intervals, decisions about removal of features is made when they become a burden, but usually they are retained if they are not in the way.

6 Conclusion

The BIT1 simulation code performs kinetic simulations of the tokamak plasma edge in 4 dimensions. Number of know-hows developed specifically for this code enable BIT1 to perform unique large-scale simulations with finest resolution in time and space. At present, code is used for design and optimisation of future fusion devices.

Our profiling study indicated that the BIT1 code has a factor 9 performance gap compared to what it would require for achieving the scientific target at the end of the Plasma-PEPSC project. We have discussed code development road map in order to enhance run efficiency of the BIT1 code and reach goals of the Plasma-PEPSC project.

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